

A Tourism Recommender System using CF approach and Matrix Factorization

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Abstract

With the development of the Internet, technology, and communication devices, the production of tourist data at all levels (hotels, restaurants, transportation, heritage, tourism events, activities, etc.) has multiplied. However, the list of possibilities provided by these web search engines (or even specialized tourism sites) and offered to tourists, can be abundant, which causes information overload. Many recommender systems have been created to help tourists plan their trips and help them find the information they are looking for. In this paper, first, the different approaches of recommender systems in the field of tourism are reviewed. Then, the proposed method of this study is presented. Primarily, similar users are identified based on their preferences and priorities and using cosine distance. If the same users have not rated the visited places, this vacancy (blank space) of rating will be filled using the ALS factoring matrix. Then, to recommend the next location to the target user, the similar users to the target user is calculated using the cosine distance, and the weighted average for the 3 top locations is calculated, and the location with the most weight is recommended to the target user. According to the results presented in Section 4, the proposed method has more accuracy, recall, and F1 in the recommendation than the CF method.

Keywords: Tourism Recommender System, CF approach, Matrix Factorization Weight Average.

1. Introduction

For many people, tourism provides an opportunity to spend their leisure time and discover new cultures. With progressing information and communication technology and the development of living standards in communities, the demand for tourism has increased sharply. Numerous factors play a role in determining the choice of tourist destination, such as predictability, availability of activities, popularity, and safety [1]. Despite the abundance of content on the World Wide Web, it is always doubtful to use this information to find a destination that meets all the criteria of a potential traveler. This is mainly because the available information is not personalized and does not match the user's request. Therefore, travel and tourism software tools tend to combine a recommender system to increase the quality of services provided. Several tourism recommendation and tour planning systems are presented [6, 4, 5, 3,2]. In

general, the design of tourism recommendation systems is difficult due to a large amount of information available and the complex and multi-layered nature of the requests and needs of tourists [7].

In the area of tourism, recommender systems can be very helpful when planning a trip or searching for services among many destinations, attractions, and activities. Specifically, these systems are defined as information filtering systems that provide the most appropriate recommendations (products, services, etc.) to customers. For example, products that are similar to other products previously they have bought and enjoyed or products that have already been welcomed by other customers with similar tastes are considered in this category [7]. The standard principle is to use the preferences and priorities of a user collected during the navigation as input, to predict how much interest this user may have about the desired item. The approaches used to estimate this

are numerous. According to the source of information used (based on the desired applications, applying knowledge, the method of developing recommendations, and the implemented algorithms) are traditionally classified by the literature in 3 categories [9,8]. Collaborative filtering, content-based filtering, knowledge-based filtering, matrix factoring, hybrid RS. Among them, Collaborative Filtering (CF) is the most widely used method in e-commerce and social media. This approach is aimed to provide destinations to visitors who have not been there yet, but they may use the habits and tastes of similar user profiles [10]. The similarity of taste between two users is calculated based on the similarity of their rating (ranking) history. However, this approach is difficult to meet the needs of tourists, because it is very difficult to find two people on a trip, with the same travel history (rank), the same places of interest, and the same experiences.

This study is aimed to provide a new approach for recommender systems in the area of tourism to help potential tourists find a destination that meets their preferences and requirements. The proposed method uses the CF approach for recommendations. After finding similar users, the tourist destinations are weighed according to the rating (rankings) given by the tourists, and the destination that has the most weight is recommended to the tourist. Weighting the destinations is one of the innovations of this study. Since some tourists may not have registered a ranking, we use the factoring matrix to create a ranking and solve the problem, which is another innovation of this research.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the literature on the most common tourism recommendation methods; Section 3 presents a description of the proposed architecture for tourism recommendation systems and its

conceptual framework. Section 4 will evaluate the proposed method and finally, Section 5 will provide conclusions and suggestions for future research.

2- Literature Review

Given that the current techniques of tourism recommendations have many innovative aspects, they can be classified in different ways depending on how the user information is analyzed and the list of items is filtered.

2-1- Collaborative filtering based recommender system

Collaborative filtering-based recommender systems recommend items that are popular among other users with similar interests. For example, the VISIT system [11] uses emotion analysis techniques (using the API) to analyze news related to tourist attractions on Twitter and Facebook and determines whether users give positive or negative comments about it. This information is displayed in green and red by the system in

its user interface so that the user can easily identify the places that visitors enjoy nowadays and the places that are not enjoyable.

In [12], the authors propose a destination recommender system that uses polling to create profiles of user preferences and item reputation. They also use collaborative filtering to predict destination rankings.

2-2- Content-based recommender system

In order to provide recommendations for the potential tourists, content-based systems are based on an analysis of content similarities between items that have already been commented on by users or items that have not yet been reviewed [13]. The method is a common technique and Widespread in tourism recommendation systems [14]. The proposed system in [15] defines a content-based recommendation method for cultural heritage. This method chooses resources based on user preferences and data, and selects commands using multi-criteria user

feedback, and makes suggestions using semantic relationships between items.

Lial et al. [16] proposed a system that suggests the destination to the user based on textual review and machine learning techniques. The system uses a semantic content approach to provide personalized recommendations based on a textual review of a hotel with an Expedia source.

Sun et al. [17] use Flickr geotagged photos as well as other background information (such as weather) to extract users' travel preferences and create their own travel history. They then use this profile to generate recommendations.

2-3- Hybrid recommender system

A combination of these approaches has been the subject of several research studies to overcome limitations and use their strengths [18]. In [19], the authors propose a hybrid recommendation model using user ratings, comments, and social data. Also in [20], the

nearest neighbors machine learning algorithms (K-NN) for CB and CF and decision tree for demographic filtering on TripAdvisor data were used, which is a combined method to optimize their benefits and overcome the cold start problem. Is. The study carried out in [21] is aimed to implement a recommender system for tourism through mobile devices using the Android operating system. The results of this study show that the combined multi-criteria method is able to provide recommendations in accordance with the user's personal preferences and previous user ranking history with high accuracy.

3- Proposed method

In the proposed system, there are m users and n items, which represent the user set as $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ and the item set as $I = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n\}$. Target user refers to the user to whom the system recommends or predicts and is denoted by u_a . Also, the available items are tourist places that users have gone to these

places and rated based on their interests and level of enjoyment. The user-item matrix, which is one of the main inputs of a recommender system, includes the ranking of users on items (locations) in the database. In other words, each row represents a user and each column represents an item.

Users describe their interests by assigning numerical ratings to items. The assigned rating creates the user profile, which compared to other profiles, in turn, is applied to consider users with similar tastes. Cosine spacing is used to find the similar user:

$$\text{Similarity}(\bar{u}_a, \bar{u}_1) = \cos(\bar{u}_a, \bar{u}_1) = \frac{\bar{u}_a \cdot \bar{u}_1}{\|\bar{u}_a\| \cdot \|\bar{u}_1\|}$$

Formula 1

Here the vector of user u_a contains all the places he/she has visited and ranked also for the vector of user u_1 which is extracted using the cosine distance of the users with the most similarity to the u_a user. Since some users may not have rated the places visited, we use the factoring matrix here. This is one of the matrix factorization models that is considered

as a list of user items. The proposed system is implemented based on user-level and item-level techniques. The system, uses a matrix factorization approach with ALS is used, which executes the rating data set into a matrix according to embedded (latent) attributes-based item and the. Therefore, when they are combined again, we get a new user matrix. The new matrix may have a missing input. In case of missing input, the system fills the space based on the similarities of the user level and the item level and refills the values based on the matrix U.

Assume M is a matrix. ALS considers this matrix and converts it to two small matrices, Y and P, where x (multiplication) together produces an approximate matrix R. Where y and p together produce an approximate R matrix. Firstly, ALS determines the values to be placed in Y and P. Random numbers and error term calculation is carried out according to the error formula, and then the frequency between the Y matrix and the p matrix is

adjusted by ALS. ALS adjusts the matrices so that the error will be reduced frequently and the task is repeated until the error time is minimized. When this task is carried out,

matrices Y and P are multiplied together. The advantage of ALS is that when matrices are multiplied, empty spaces in the original Matrix M are filled (Figure 1).

Figure1. The process of the ALS algorithm.

After the above operation, the 3 users that are most similar to the user u_a are extracted, and the weighted average of items (places) that have not been visited by user u_a so far are calculated using Formula 2:

$$\text{Weighted average} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i i_n}{n \times \text{maxrate}}$$

Formula 2

where r is the rates that the user has given to the visited places, i_n is nth place, n number of places and maxrate is the highest score that

can be given to the places (number 5 is considered). The place with the highest weighted average score is recommended to the user u_a .

4- Experiment

In this section, an experimental study of proposed recommender model is explained. Also, the result of the execution of the proposed model is compared with

conventional and traditional approaches to evaluate their efficiency.

4-1- Dataset

The data set used in our study is from TripAdvisor, which for each tourist destination, the data includes an overview of the destination (eg name, address, price, average rating) such as ratings (1 to 5 stars). The dataset contains 980 visitors to 11 destinations. In this paper, to verify the experiment, we use cross-validation is used for items, and 20% of users are considered as test users and the remaining 80% as training users.

4-2- Performance Metrics

Accuracy and readability are the practical criteria in data recovery area which determines the proportion of documents retrieved by the system to the user's needs. To

express these two criteria, we can use the same expressions as in the clutter matrix used.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Recall} &= \text{TP}/(\text{TP}+\text{FN}) \\ \text{Precision} &= \text{TP}/(\text{TP}+\text{FP}) \\ \text{F-measure(F1)} &= \frac{2 * \text{Recall} * \text{Precision}}{(\text{Recall} + \text{Precision})} \end{aligned}$$

Formula 3

A precision measure is a ratio of the number of effective recommendations to the total number of recommendations provided to an active user. Recall measure is a ratio of the number of effective recommendations to the number of user desirable items. The F-Measure is the weighted average of the precision and recall that is calculated by the ratio of multiplication of two numbers to the sum of them. The value of all three measures is in [0, 1] and 1 is the best value [22]. Figure 2 shows the value of these three measures for the proposed recommendation strategy with basic recommender method.

Fig2- The comparison of the value of evaluation measures for the 2 methods

According to the above figure, Recall criterion in both methods has the highest result for location recommendation. Also, the accuracy of the proposed method compared to the basic method in the location recommendation is 51.31%. Finally, 63.90% was recorded for the F1 criterion using the proposed method in recommending the next location to the target user. In general, the use of the factorization matrix and the weight criterion proposed in this paper increases the accuracy, recall, and F1 by 2 times compared to the CF method alone in recommending the next locations.

5- Conclusion

Available information for the public has a significant impact on the choice of travel destination. Tourism recommender systems can help users deal with information overload. This paper suggests a method for recommending destinations to tourists to help them determine the most appropriate destination. In the proposed method, similar users are first identified according to their preferences and priorities using a cosine distance. If the user has not rated the visited places using the ALS factoring matrix, this

blank space is filled. Then, to recommend the next location to the target user, the similarity of the same users to the target user is also calculated using the cosine distance, and the weighted average for the top 3 locations is calculated, and the location with the most weight is recommended to the target user. According to the results presented in Section 4, the proposed method has more accuracy, recall, and F1 in the recommendation than the CF method. The limitation of this study is the small number of experimental samples that we had to use due to the lack of more data.

For future work, users' comments can be used along with the factorization and weighted average matrix, where the comments are analyzed using emotion analysis, and depending on whether the comments are positive or negative, the ratings given to each item increase or decrease and affects the weighted average.

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